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Abstract. This article reveals digital technologies, the stages of their development, and the possibilities of use in a post-industrial society.

Basic words. post-industrial society, digital pedagogy, digital competence, digital skills, history of digital technologies

Introduction. Today we live in a post-industrial society, in which, as a result of the scientific and technological revolution and significant growth in income, priority has shifted from the production of primary goods to the production of services. A post-industrial society is a society in which the service sector has priority development and exceeds the volume of industrial production and agricultural production.

The development of digital pedagogy was driven by digital technologies and its purpose was to provide the technological capabilities of digital technologies as a means of learning. At the same time, as a result of the interaction of subjects of the educational process, the quality of education partially increased and the emergence of a new quality appeared. Such a scientific and technological revolution has led to the emergence of new terms as a new reality, such as digital economy, digital educational space, digital pedagogy, digital medicine and healthcare, etc.

In society, modern teachers are constantly faced with the challenge of improving education and teaching methods to meet changing requirements. To be successful in the future, teaching and learning needs to know how to use digital technologies to achieve digital literacy and digital competencies.

In fact, modern young people actively interact in two worlds - real and virtual at the same time. In this regard, both teachers and students need to have a set of digital literacy and digital competencies to effectively organize educational activities [2].

Main part. Digital competence involves the ongoing acquisition of the ability to critically, reliably, safely and effectively identify and use communication and information technologies in all areas of life. In the last century, many effective technologies were introduced and improved in the education system, among which digital technologies occupy a special place. Digitalization was expected to lead to a revolution not only in the economic sphere, but also in teaching and learning, creating a number of important improvements and breakthroughs in terms of equal access to education and the rapid growth of educational services.

In the history of the development of digital educational technologies, three main stages can be distinguished (Figure 1).

Figure 1. History of digital technology and education system

Pre-digital educational technologies is film, radio and television. They were included in the educational process in the 1920s. Television came a little later, in the 1950s. These innovations have been slower to take hold in rural, regional and remote areas. At that time, these technologies were not available to everyone at home and were not adapted for special educational purposes. Ideas of efficiency and productivity spread rapidly with the advent of industrialization, and the strategies became educational technologies that could be accessed directly and efficiently by large numbers of students. The combination of media, especially television, has become an effective mechanism for expanding audiences, which is considered to be the closest thing to real-life experiences. Public opinion of these technologies and their benefits was so positive that some students were able to learn everything they needed for an education by watching movies and television shows or listening to radio programs, which was in line with the popular educational views of the time. This approach to education is usually called objectivism [3].

Digital technologies and the Internet. Entering the educational process in the 90s of the twentieth century, the third “century” of educational technologies is the era of digital technologies and Internet communications. In particular, the era of using computers and other devices connected via local networks began. Access to the Internet and distance learning opportunities have led to the democratization of education and increased access to educational services. By the late 1990s, most schools had Internet access and some form of Internet use [1].

At the beginning of 2000, the opportunity arose to take advantage of the more dynamic capabilities of the Internet. This has resulted in people living in the community being able to communicate online and create content online. The main aspects of this change are that Opera, Google Chrome, Yandex and other search programs began to use the natural language search capabilities of the Internet.

Summary. In conclusion, the main aspect of digitalization is that digital technologies, which become complex and demanding, take their place in the public consciousness. Despite progress in introducing technology into teaching, there are also problems in using digital opportunities in the practice of teachers and educators. For example, limited ability to acquire the latest digital technologies or selective use of available information after accessing the Internet, difficulties in sorting, etc. However, today the use of computers, electronic boards, telephones, the Internet and software serves to improve the quality and efficiency of education.

References.

1. Deja, M. Digital transformation readiness: perspectives on academia and library outcomes in information literacy / M. Deja, D. Rak, B. Bell // The Journal of Academic Librarianship. — 2021. — № 47 (5). — R. 102403. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.acalib.2021.102403>
2. КАЮМОВА Н. А. THE NEW TECHNOLOGIES IN THE ORGANIZATION OF THE ELECTRONIC LEARNING ENVIRONMENT IN HIGHER EDUCATION // Современное образование (Узбекистан). – 2021. – №. 2. – С. 64-73.
3. Каюмова Н. А., Суропов Б. М. ПСИХОЛОГО-ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИЕ АСПЕКТЫ В ПРОЦЕССЕ ОБУЧЕНИЯ ИНФОРМАЦИОННО-КОММУНИКАЦИОННЫЕ ТЕХНОЛОГИИ // Интернаука. – 2019. – №. 28. – С. 66-67.
4. Kayumova, N. A. "The conditions of the information-educational system of education and the training of teachers in the field of information and communication technologies. Monograph. T.:“.” Science and technology (2015).
5. Nasiba Q., Tukhtaeva G. The value of the life cycle in the design of information systems // central asian journal of education and computer sciences (cajecs). – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 6. – С. 24-28.